

#4

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>CREATING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Crucial at project development stage and used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small groups or large consortia</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Non-expert users, no technical knowledge required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>30 mins-1.5 hrs (depending on group size & extent of discussion). At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #1, 3, 16.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Photo by [Anshu A on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Assess cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised.
- Draw attention to different norms held by different actor categories, while also allowing individuals (and their individual perspectives/norms/preferences) to be taken into account.
- Assess potential for group conflict to occur, attune the facilitator to potential for conflict, and provide tool to actively avoid conflict
- Establish culture & context-specific sensitive ground rules for how multi-actor groups work together
- Establish ground-rules for how multi-actor groups work with external actors.
- Update ground rules as necessary, regarding how multi-actor groups work together and how they work with external stakeholders.

Background and Logic

Multi-actor projects involve diverse actors who are directly involved in interactive innovation, and bring different types of knowledge to the process. A rich process of interactive innovation must tap into distinctive types of perspectives, experiences and ideas held by the different actors involved (this is called 'emic' knowledge). The whole logic of the multi-actor approach (and interactive innovation) is to avoid innovation being dominated by top-down, generic knowledge or knowledge that is traditionally perceived as 'expert' knowledge (this is called 'etic' knowledge).

However, because interactive innovation involves diverse types of people, different cultural, social, professional etc. norms must often be negotiated. If cultural norms are not assessed at the beginning of a process/project so that they can be observed and respected by actors throughout the process, it may transpire that some cultural norms are not observed/respected, and that other cultural norms dominate the process/project. This hampers interactive innovation, because actors may not contribute fully to the process and because they may feel that their knowledge, perspectives etc. are not valid, valuable or respected in the process. Conditions must be established where all actors feel that their norms are respected, so that they can contribute their knowledge as fully as possible to the interactive innovation process.

This tool assesses cultural norms and establishes 'ground rules' that can be referred to regularly in the interactive innovation process. Internal ground rules (in a multi-actor group) can be extended, when working with external stakeholders, to represent and include their ground rules. Ground rules can be periodically assessed/updated as required, as the interactive innovation process evolves to confront new challenges. It is important that stakeholder profiling exercises also take into account gender and diversity issues.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #1, which identifies actors involved in interactive innovation according to their 'actor identifier/category' (the actor cohort they are representing in the interactive innovation process). Following the use of Tool #1, this Tool can be used to dig into their cultural norms and identify ground rules based on those norms.

Materials

- Template (adapted from Ginka Toegel & Jean-Louis Barsoux, 2015) to assess & uncover cultural norms.
- Flipchart paper
- Thick dark markers
- Word processing software, if preparing a professional representation of the group's ground rules

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Explain the Logic and Principles of Multi-actor Work

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- Optionally
 - » Show the 'multi-actor work' animation, which shows the importance of unearthing actors' individual and different customs, experiences, perspectives and ideas for innovation. This sensitises participants to the nature and focus of the exercise.
 - » The animation could also be sent by email/ WhatsApp in advance of the meeting, helping them to prepare for the content of the meeting.
 - » Use the template (or just parts of it) to facilitate a discussion of team-based cooperation, and the cultural norms that are/not acceptable to different actor types involved in the process. Choose just parts of the template, as appropriate to the nature of the group.

Step 2: Preparation for Use of Template in Step 3

- The template may be issued (in print form, or by email if holding an online meeting) to group participants in different ways, depending on the nature of the group.
- Explain that the template is used to sensitise people to different cultural, professional and other norms, so that they can be mindful of these norms in the interactive innovation process; and so that the facilitator/s can assess norms to ensure they are respected in the process.
- In the meeting, allow participants to read through the template, taking each section in turn & answering questions in relation to each section before moving on to the next.
- Emphasise to participants to try to think about 'norms in their world' and to think about what would be distinctive of the actor category they are representing, but also their own individual perspectives.

- To make the exercise more specific to actor categories (rather than personal characteristics), change the wording to 'in a (actor category) world', e.g. 'in a farmer's world...'. Each participant would use the appropriate actor category, depending on what category they are representing in the interactive innovation process.
- Encourage participants to ask questions as needed, when they are completing the template, mindful that some participants may be more accustomed than others to completing such templates.
- Participants may be asked to complete the template in different ways, depending on the nature of the group and the time available.
 - » A whole group discussion may be held, where participants are asked to take turns in answering the 'in my world...' statements
 - » Actors can be split into smaller groups where they answer the 'in my world statements'
 - » Optionally, allow participants to choose particular 'in my word statements' that are particularly relevant to their world
- Whatever approach is taken, it is important for the facilitator/s to record the answers. Though it isn't necessary to record who said what, it is important to record answers according to the corresponding actor category.
- Consent may be sought to audio-record the discussions for transcription (adhering to appropriate data protection practices), for the facilitator/s sole use.

Step 3: Template to Assess Norms

Template adapted from Ginka Toegel & Jean-Louis Barsoux (2015), based on 'Act, Think, Speak, Feel'
<https://hbr.org/2016/06/how-to-preempt-team-conflict>

ACT:

"In your world...

- ...how important are punctuality and time limits?
- ...are there consequences of being late or missing deadlines?
- ...what is a comfortable physical distance for interacting in the workplace?
- ...should people volunteer for assignments or wait to be nominated?
- ...what group behaviors are valued (helping others, not complaining)?"

SPEAK:

"In your world...

- ...is a promise an aspiration or a guarantee?
- ...which is most important: directness or harmony?
- ...are irony and sarcasm appreciated?
- ...do interruptions signal interest or rudeness?
- ...does silence mean reflection or disengagement?
- ...should dissenting views be aired in public or discussed off-line?
- ...is unsolicited feedback welcome?"

THINK:

"In your world...

- ...is uncertainty viewed as a threat or an opportunity?
- ...what's more important: the big picture or the details?
- ...is it better to be reliable or flexible?
- ...what is the attitude toward failure?
- ...how do people tolerate deviations from the plan?"

FEEL:

"In your world...

- ...what emotions (positive and negative) are acceptable and unacceptable to display in a business context?
- ...how do people express anger or enthusiasm?
- ...how would you react if you were annoyed with a teammate (with silence, body language, humor, through a third party)?"

Step 5: Identify Ground Rules

- It is important to take a break in the process, as the previous steps involve intensive work.
- Explain that the objective is to identify some important ground rules for the interactive innovation process, so that all participants feel respected and thus feel free and safe to contribute their ideas.
- Suggest some simple ground rules first, like the 'housekeeping' ones pictured.
- Ask participants to identify any other simple rules (this gets the process of identifying rules going)
- Then encourage participants to reflect on the norms that have been identified in previous steps, and to identify more rules to ensure participants feel respected in how they work together.
- Add rules on sticky-note to flip chart paper & finally, agree all rules with participants

Step 6: Ongoing assessment

- For all meetings where people are intended to work together openly and creatively, open the meeting by placing the poster showing ground rules in a visible location throughout the meeting.
- Refer briefly to the content at the beginning of the meeting
- Invite people to add new ground rules if they wish to, by writing a new rule on a sticky-note and placing it on the poster of ground rules.
- At the end of every meeting, if a new ground rule/s has been added to the poster, facilitate a discussion about its importance. Ask participants if they thought any of their ground rules were particularly important during the meeting and invite suggestions for new ground rules.

